

Correlation of Photography with Blood in the Urine

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ABSTRACT

The people who are interested in photography, are likely to be infected with hematuria. In the present study, we elaborated on the relation between photography with blood in the urine. This study shows likeness or dislikeness for photography. 1 male has blood in his urine and he shows likeness for photography. 8 males don't have any blood in their urine. They also show likeness for photography. 6 females show the presence of blood in their urine but they also show likeness for photography. 46 females don't have blood in their urine they also show likeness for photography. On the other hand, 2 males have blood in their urine and they show dislikeness toward photography. 6 males don't have any blood in their urine but they also show dislikeness for photography. 3 females have blood in their urine but they don't like photography. 12 females having no blood in their urine also don't like photography.

1. Introduction

Photography is an emerging field nowadays. That is why many people take it as a profession and maintain their livelihood. As we know the main purpose of photography is communication. Very few people take pictures only to please themselves. The main benefit of photography is to improve your imagination level. It also enhances our capabilities to observe things that are present in our surroundings. It also increases our capacity to think well on a logical basis. A person who has a great intellectual level and also great observational level of seeing the things will become good and professional photographer. Because photography is an art and the person who adopts this profession called as artist [1-2].

Blood in urine can be defined as presence of blood in urine called as hematuria. This disease may be painful while urination. Blood in urine is the obvious indication of severe disorder of urinary tract of person. And the urinary blood only visible under the microscope [3]. Your doctor can check the blood in your urine. Blood in urine is also the indication of bladder cancer. The cause of blood in urine is due to an infection, stones in kidney or bladder and benign kidney diseases. During urination burning or pain may indicate the severe symptoms of STDs. Inflammation in the filtering system of kidney also the cause of infections in urinary tract [4].

The main objective of this study to locate the correlation between photography and blood in urine as the people who are interested in photography, they are likely to be infected with hematuria.

2. Materials and methods

Total 100 numbers of students of Bahauddin Zakariya University are involved in this study. We called the student and took blood samples from each student. We also performed lab test to check blood in urine. We performed dipstick test in lab after taking the sample from every student. You dipped the stick in to the sample of the urine for appropriate period of time. After specific time you got results that the person's urine contains blood or not. This dipstick test also performed to check the number of leukocytes in urine.

Study design

This project is design to elaborate the relation between blood in urine and photography.

Statistical analysis

The calculations of the present study are operating by MS Excel.

Objective

This project is done to check the likeness and dislikeness of photography according to blood in urine.

3. Results and Discussions

Gender	Photography likeness		Photography dislikeness	
	Existence of blood in urine	Non-existence of blood in urine	Existence of blood in urine	Non-existence of blood in urine
Male	1	8	2	6
Female	6	46	3	12

From the table we conclude that majority of the students show their likeness for photography. But very few people show dislikeness for photography. 1 male having blood in urine and he show likeness for photography. 8 males don't have any blood in urine. They also show likeness for photography. 6 females show the presence of blood in their urine but they also show likeness for photography. 46 females don't have blood in urine they also show likeness for photography. On the other hand, 2 males having the blood in urine and they show dislikeness for photography. 6 males don't have any blood in urine but they also show dislikeness for photography. 3 females having blood in urine but they don't like photography. 12 females having no blood in urine they also don't like photography. This questionnaire-based study is important for such type of research to get acceptable and authentic outcomes and for valuable illustrations [5].

4. Conclusion

From result it is concluded that most of the people don't have the blood in urine and show likeness for photography. Few people show dislikeness for photography and also having blood in their urine.

Declarations

Source of Funding

This research did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

Availability of data and material

The authors are willing to share the data and material according to relevant needs.

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